

Supplementary Information for “Antimicrobial Peptide LL37 is Potent Against Non-Growing *Escherichia coli* Cells Despite a Slower Action Rate” by Mohammadi, Savcedo and Taheri-Araghi

A. Live-cell Imaging Technique

In this study, we used patterned agarose gel along with live microscopy to monitor the activity of *E. coli* cells in the presence of LL37 peptides. We utilized a method similar to those previously used in the literature [1, 2]. In this method, to distribute the cells beneath the agarose pad effectively, patterned channels were created within the agarose gel. This approach not only enabled precise cell placement but also significantly reduced evaporation by housing the gel in a closed environment. Such an arrangement was crucial for conducting long-term microscopy studies at an optimal temperature of 37°C.

Figure 1 demonstrates the steps involved in preparing the samples. The process began with the preparation of a polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) chip, which was cast on a custom-designed silicon wafer. This chip, featuring parallel indentations, was then securely attached to a microscope slide. This step was to ensure stability during the gel patterning process. Subsequently, a PDMS was cut to be placed on a microscope slide to form the housing for the gel. The PDMS cut created a groove in the middle that contained a profile on the edge and a wider opening for the agarose gel. Next, low-melt agarose gel (in liquid phase) was poured into this setup and covered by the patterned PDMS chip. After allowing about 10 minutes for the gel to solidify, the stamp was removed, leaving behind distinct patterns on the gel.

For microscopy, samples were prepared by plating 2 μ L of culture onto a microscope slide, which was then covered with the patterned gel housing. This method ensured that the cells were directed into the channels patterned within the gel, allowing for optimal observation conditions. A phase contrast image (Figure D) showcases cells situated under the patterned gel housing, providing a clear visualization of the cells in their designated channels. This image serves as a testament to the effectiveness of our live-cell microscopy technique, demonstrating the precision with which cells can be observed and studied under these specially designed conditions.

B. Images of the Minimum Bactericidal Concentration Experiments

We determined the Minimum Bactericidal Concentration (MBC) of LL37 peptides by assessing the viability of *E. coli* cells following exposure to varying concentrations of LL37

Fig. S1. Illustration of steps for live cell microscopy using patterned agarose gel. **(A)** A PDMS chip, cast on a custom-designed silicon wafer, is attached to a microscope slide to ensure stability during the patterning process. The chip has parallel indentations, allowing for the patterning of the gel. **(B)** The gel housing is formed using a layer of PDMS on a microscope slide. The groove in the middle contains a profile on the edge and a wider opening where the liquid low-melt agarose gel is poured and then covered by the patterned PDMS chip. After 10 minutes, the gel solidifies, and the stamp is removed, leaving behind patterns in the gel. **(C)** Microscopy samples are created by plating $2 \mu\text{L}$ of culture onto a microscope slide and afterward covering it with the patterned gel housing. The cells find their way into the channels patterned in the gel. **(D)** A phase contrast image depicting cells under the patterned gel housing conditions.

as detailed in the Materials and Methods section.

The results of these MBC assays are visually presented in Figure S2. The figure shows four 96-well plates—two plates on the left correspond to the experiments conducted on exponentially growing cells, and the two plates on the right correspond to the experiments conducted on stationary phase cells.

Fig. S2. Images of 96-well plates used to determine the MBC of LL37 for *E. coli* cells. The two plates on the left represent the results from exponentially growing cells, and the two plates on the right correspond to the results from stationary phase cells. The LL37 concentrations used ranged from 0.3 μM to 1.125 μM for exponentially growing cells and from 0.075 μM to 0.900 μM for stationary phase cells. Each condition was tested in 16 replicates across two plates, with each plate representing a different biological sample. The lowest concentration of LL37 that resulted in complete inhibition of cell growth (MBC) is indicated by a red dot on the images. Growth was assessed after transferring 10 μL of culture from each well to LB-agar plates and incubating for 16 to 24 hours at 37°C.

C. Caption of supplementary video

Video S1: Visualization of cellular response to nutrient deprivation in a microfluidic device. This video illustrates sample individual *E. coli* cells over multiple generations as they undergo transitions between rich defined medium (RDM) and a nutrient-deprived buffer. Initially, cells are observed growing in RDM, followed by a switch to the buffer for three hours, where we observe the impact on the growth rate and division delay. The rapid transition to the buffer results in a quick drop in the elongation rate of individual cells to zero, with a subsequent delay in the division rate. After three hours in the buffer, where growth is largely arrested, the environment is switched back to RDM, where we observe the recovery of cell growth and division rates.

- [2] D. G. Priest, N. Tanaka, Y. Tanaka, and Y. Taniguchi, *Scientific Reports* **7**, 17750 (2017).